

Cyclic Integration by Parts

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Abstract

Integration by parts is a tool used by every calculus student. The technique gives good results more often than not, when it does not, it is usually because the result yielded a new awkward integral that takes the same form as the original one resulting in a loop. When integration by parts is applied to certain integrals, the original integral sometimes reappears, this leads to confusion sometimes, making students question if they chose the right technique or there are mistakes. Turns out there is no mistake after all as now we have to solve the integral algebraically. We present a general theorem for the family $\int e^{ax} \sin(bx) dx$, work through examples of increasing complexity, and conclude with a classification table. A brief historical note familiarises the reader with the technique and explains why $\int \sec^3 x dx$ is a classical example.

1 Historical Origin of Integration by Parts

The method of integration by parts has been used for a long time, although the modern form was formulated by Brook Taylor (1715). However, the underlying relationship appears earlier in the work of Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz, who recognized the product rule for differentiation:

$$\frac{d}{dx}[u(x)v(x)] = u'(x)v(x) + u(x)v'(x).$$

Integrating both sides with respect to x gives the common formula:

$$\int u(x)v'(x) dx = u(x)v(x) - \int u'(x)v(x) dx.$$

The formula appears explicitly in Taylor's **Methodus Incrementorum Directa et Inversa (1715)** and was later popularized by Leonhard Euler in his calculus work. The technique became the go to solution by the mid-eighteenth century and remains so today.

2 A General Theorem: $\int e^{ax} \sin(bx) dx$

The family $e^{ax} \sin(bx)$ and $e^{ax} \cos(bx)$ are the simplest cyclic integrals. The following theorem generalizes the classic example.

For constants $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$ with $a^2 + b^2 \neq 0$,

$$\int e^{ax} \sin(bx) dx = \frac{e^{ax}}{a^2 + b^2} (a \sin(bx) - b \cos(bx)) + C.$$

Proof. Let $I = \int e^{ax} \sin(bx) dx$. Choose $u = \sin(bx)$, $dv = e^{ax} dx$. Then $du = b \cos(bx) dx$ and $v = \frac{1}{a} e^{ax}$ (assuming $a \neq 0$; if $a = 0$, then the integral reduces to $\int \sin(bx) dx$).

Integration by parts gives:

$$I = \frac{1}{a}e^{ax} \sin(bx) - \frac{b}{a} \int e^{ax} \cos(bx) dx.$$

Now let $J = \int e^{ax} \cos(bx) dx$. Apply integration by parts again with $u = \cos(bx)$, $dv = e^{ax} dx$:

$$J = \frac{1}{a}e^{ax} \cos(bx) + \frac{b}{a} \int e^{ax} \sin(bx) dx = \frac{1}{a}e^{ax} \cos(bx) + \frac{b}{a}I.$$

Substitute this into the equation for I :

$$I = \frac{1}{a}e^{ax} \sin(bx) - \frac{b}{a} \left(\frac{1}{a}e^{ax} \cos(bx) + \frac{b}{a}I \right).$$

Simplify:

$$I = \frac{1}{a}e^{ax} \sin(bx) - \frac{b}{a^2}e^{ax} \cos(bx) - \frac{b^2}{a^2}I.$$

$$I + \frac{b^2}{a^2}I = \frac{1}{a}e^{ax} \sin(bx) - \frac{b}{a^2}e^{ax} \cos(bx),$$

$$I \left(1 + \frac{b^2}{a^2} \right) = \frac{1}{a}e^{ax} \sin(bx) - \frac{b}{a^2}e^{ax} \cos(bx).$$

Since $1 + b^2/a^2 = (a^2 + b^2)/a^2$, multiply both sides by a^2 :

$$I(a^2 + b^2) = ae^{ax} \sin(bx) - be^{ax} \cos(bx).$$

Solving for I yields the mentioned formula. For $a = 0$, direct integration gives $-\frac{1}{b} \cos(bx) + C$, which agrees with the limit of the formula as $a \rightarrow 0$. \square

A similar derivation gives:

$$\int e^{ax} \cos(bx) dx = \frac{e^{ax}}{a^2 + b^2} (a \cos(bx) + b \sin(bx)) + C.$$

These formulas are worth remembering as they can save time in examinations!!!

3 Example 1: The Simplest Case ($a = 1, b = 1$)

Applying the theorem with $a = 1$ and $b = 1$:

$$\int e^x \sin x dx = \frac{e^x}{1^2 + 1^2} (1 \cdot \sin x - 1 \cdot \cos x) + C = \frac{e^x}{2} (\sin x - \cos x) + C.$$

This is the prototypical cyclic integral. The recurrence appears after two applications of integration by parts, and the coefficient $k = -1$ leads to the factor 2 in the denominator.

4 Example 2: The Cosine Counterpart

For $\int e^x \cos x dx$, the theorem gives:

$$\int e^x \cos x dx = \frac{e^x}{2} (\sin x + \cos x) + C.$$

5 Example 3: A Trig Square

The integral $\int e^x \sin^2 x dx$ requires some manipulation before the cyclic pattern emerges. Using the identity $\sin^2 x = (1 - \cos 2x)/2$:

$$\int e^x \sin^2 x dx = \frac{1}{2} \int e^x dx - \frac{1}{2} \int e^x \cos 2x dx = \frac{1}{2} e^x - \frac{1}{2} K,$$

where $K = \int e^x \cos 2x dx$. Applying the theorem to K with $a = 1$, $b = 2$:

$$K = \frac{e^x}{1^2 + 2^2} (1 \cdot \cos 2x + 2 \cdot \sin 2x) = \frac{e^x}{5} (\cos 2x + 2 \sin 2x).$$

Thus:

$$\int e^x \sin^2 x dx = \frac{1}{2} e^x - \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{e^x}{5} (\cos 2x + 2 \sin 2x) + C = \frac{e^x}{10} (5 - \cos 2x - 2 \sin 2x) + C.$$

6 Example 4: $\int \sec^3 x dx$ — A Classical Example

The integral of $\sec^3 x$ is common in many calculus textbooks as an application of integration by parts. Its reputation comes from two conclusions: firstly, the reduction formula for $\int \sec^n x dx$ is itself a recurrence; secondly, $\sec^3 x$ is the smallest odd power of secant that requires integration by parts (since $\int \sec x dx$ is solved by a different substitution).

Let $I = \int \sec^3 x dx$. Write $\sec^3 x = \sec x \cdot \sec^2 x$ and apply integration by parts with $u = \sec x$, $dv = \sec^2 x dx$. Then $du = \sec x \tan x dx$ and $v = \tan x$:

$$I = \sec x \tan x - \int \sec x \tan^2 x dx.$$

Using the identity $\tan^2 x = \sec^2 x - 1$,

$$I = \sec x \tan x - \int \sec x (\sec^2 x - 1) dx = \sec x \tan x - \int \sec^3 x dx + \int \sec x dx.$$

But $\int \sec^3 x dx = I$. Hence:

$$I = \sec x \tan x - I + \ln |\sec x + \tan x| + C.$$

Solving for I :

$$\begin{aligned} 2I &= \sec x \tan x + \ln |\sec x + \tan x| + C, \\ I &= \frac{1}{2} \sec x \tan x + \frac{1}{2} \ln |\sec x + \tan x| + C. \end{aligned}$$

This problem is oddly satisfying because the recurrence vanishes after only one integration, not two. The factor $k = -1$ appears again.

7 Example 5: Non-Unit Coefficients ($k = -\frac{9}{4}$)

The general formula above handles any a and b . For instance, with $a = 2$, $b = 3$:

$$\int e^{2x} \sin(3x) dx = \frac{e^{2x}}{4+9} (2 \sin(3x) - 3 \cos(3x)) + C = \frac{e^{2x}}{13} (2 \sin(3x) - 3 \cos(3x)) + C.$$

Direct derivation via integration by parts yields the intermediate equation:

$$I = \frac{1}{2} e^{2x} \sin(3x) - \frac{3}{4} e^{2x} \cos(3x) - \frac{9}{4} I,$$

so $k = -9/4$ and $1 - k = 13/4$. The algebra is similar to previous cases; only the arithmetic changes.

8 Example 6: A Cyclic Integral with Hyperbolic Functions

The recurrence pattern also appears in hyperbolic functions. Recall that $\sinh(bx)$ and $\cosh(bx)$ satisfy:

$$\frac{d}{dx} \sinh(bx) = b \cosh(bx), \quad \frac{d}{dx} \cosh(bx) = b \sinh(bx).$$

Thus the same algebraic recurrence that works for \sin and \cos also works for \sinh and \cosh . Consider:

$$I = \int e^{ax} \sinh(bx) dx.$$

Let $u = \sinh(bx)$, $dv = e^{ax} dx$. Then $du = b \cosh(bx) dx$ and $v = \frac{1}{a} e^{ax}$ (assuming $a \neq 0$). Integration by parts yields:

$$I = \frac{1}{a} e^{ax} \sinh(bx) - \frac{b}{a} \int e^{ax} \cosh(bx) dx.$$

Now let $J = \int e^{ax} \cosh(bx) dx$. Apply integration by parts with $u = \cosh(bx)$, $dv = e^{ax} dx$:

$$J = \frac{1}{a} e^{ax} \cosh(bx) + \frac{b}{a} \int e^{ax} \sinh(bx) dx = \frac{1}{a} e^{ax} \cosh(bx) + \frac{b}{a} I.$$

Substitute back:

$$I = \frac{1}{a} e^{ax} \sinh(bx) - \frac{b}{a} \left(\frac{1}{a} e^{ax} \cosh(bx) + \frac{b}{a} I \right).$$

Simplify:

$$I = \frac{1}{a} e^{ax} \sinh(bx) - \frac{b}{a^2} e^{ax} \cosh(bx) - \frac{b^2}{a^2} I.$$

$$I + \frac{b^2}{a^2} I = \frac{1}{a} e^{ax} \sinh(bx) - \frac{b}{a^2} e^{ax} \cosh(bx),$$

$$I \left(1 + \frac{b^2}{a^2} \right) = \frac{1}{a} e^{ax} \sinh(bx) - \frac{b}{a^2} e^{ax} \cosh(bx).$$

Multiply both sides by a^2 :

$$I(a^2 + b^2) = ae^{ax} \sinh(bx) - be^{ax} \cosh(bx).$$

Thus:

$$\int e^{ax} \sinh(bx) dx = \frac{e^{ax}}{a^2 + b^2} (a \sinh(bx) - b \cosh(bx)) + C.$$

Similarly,

$$\int e^{ax} \cosh(bx) dx = \frac{e^{ax}}{a^2 + b^2} (a \cosh(bx) + b \sinh(bx)) + C.$$

For the special case $a = 0$, the integrals reduce to $\frac{1}{b} \cosh(bx) + C$ and $\frac{1}{b} \sinh(bx) + C$ respectively, consistent with the limit of the formulas as $a \rightarrow 0$.

9 The General Recurrence Pattern

To generalise the above examples, we can write the original integral I in the equation:

$$I = A + kI,$$

where A is an expression containing no integrals and k is a constant. Solving:

$$I - kI = A, \quad I(1 - k) = A, \quad I = \frac{A}{1 - k} + C \quad (k \neq 1).$$

If $k = 1$, the equation reduces to $I = A + I$, which forces $A = 0$. If $A \neq 0$ when $k = 1$, then a computational error has occurred.

This algebraic resolution is the central to this study. Once the recurrence is recognized, no further integration is required.

10 A Classification of Cyclic Integrals

The following patterns often produce cyclic integrals:

Pattern	Examples
$e^{ax} \sin(bx)$ or $e^{ax} \cos(bx)$	Section 3 (general formula)
$e^{ax} \sin^2(bx)$ or $e^{ax} \cos^2(bx)$	Section 5 (requires trig identity first)
$\sec^n x$ with odd $n \geq 3$	Section 6 ($\sec^3 x$)
$\csc^n x$ with odd $n \geq 3$	$\csc^3 x$ (similar method)

Products of polynomials with exponentials or trigonometric functions do *not* cycle; they reduce in degree after each integration by parts and terminate after a finite number of steps.

11 Practice Problems

- $\int e^{3x} \cos(2x) dx$
- $\int \csc^3 x dx$

3. $\int e^x \cos^2 x \, dx$
4. $\int e^{-x} \sin(4x) \, dx$
5. $\int e^x \sin x \cos x \, dx$
6. $\int \sec^5 x \, dx$ (uses a reduction formula)
7. Derive the general formula for $\int e^{ax} \cos(bx) \, dx$ from the theorem in Section 3.

12 Solutions to Practice Problems

1. $\frac{e^{3x}}{13}(3 \cos 2x + 2 \sin 2x) + C$
2. $-\frac{1}{2} \csc x \cot x + \frac{1}{2} \ln |\csc x - \cot x| + C$
3. $\frac{e^x}{2} + \frac{e^x}{10}(\sin 2x - \cos 2x) + C$
4. $-\frac{e^{-x}}{17}(\sin 4x + 4 \cos 4x) + C$
5. $\frac{e^x}{8}(\sin 2x - \cos 2x) + C$ (use $\sin x \cos x = \frac{1}{2} \sin 2x$)
6. $\frac{1}{4} \sec^3 x \tan x + \frac{3}{8} \sec x \tan x + \frac{3}{8} \ln |\sec x + \tan x| + C$
7. Differentiate the claimed formula or apply the same method as the sine case.

13 Conclusion

Cyclic integration by parts transforms a calculus problem into an algebraic equation. The recurrences are often resolved algebraically. This method solves a wide class of integrals, including the exponential-trigonometric family, trigonometric squares, and secant powers. The general formula $\int e^{ax} \sin(bx) \, dx$ provides a compact insight. Recognizing the pattern early saves computational effort and familiarizes one with the algebra behind the theorem.

References

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